

Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ : A Triphenylphosphine Complex of Molybdenum(III) and its Reactions

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A series of triphenylphosphine complexes of molybdenum(III) are described. The parent compound, Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ has been prepared by reaction of Mo(py)₃Cl₃ with PPh₃ and a *trans*-meridional structure (C_{2v}) is proposed. Others resulted from its reaction with CH₃COCH₃, CH₃CN, NO, H₂, and the reaction stoichiometries are established.

Various tertiaryphosphine complexes of lower valent molybdenum are known, but those of molybdenum(III)¹ are limited in number and structural information is available in few cases. The present communication describes a new compound, 15-electron Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ and its reactions. The reaction stoichiometries have been established and the products characterized.

Results and Discussion

Phosphination was made by triphenylphosphine (TPP) on non-electrolytic Mo(py)₃Cl₃, prepared² from the reaction of (NH₄)₂[Mo(H₂O)Cl₅] and pyridine. In the reaction, TPP replaces only two pyridine molecules giving Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃. Mo^{III} on phosphination by TPP, acquires significant aerobic stability when dry but undergoes hydrolysis in water forming hydrated Mo^{II} oxide. The ir spectrum of the compound indicates the presence of both pyridine and TPP in the molecule. The molar conductance data (Table 1) of Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ in different organic solvents indicate the molecule to be non-electrolyte. Brenciđ², from X-ray crystallography, established that the starting material Mo(py)₃Cl₃ is of

meridional/*trans*-octahedral structure. The reflectance spectrum of Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ gives maxima at 17.24, 18.18, 20.20, 21.27, 23.25, 24.39, 30.30 and 37.73 kK respectively. The spectrum conforms to that of Mo(py)₃Cl₃ with C_{2v} structure³. CV measurements on Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ in acetonitrile (0.1 M TEAP) gives an irreversible reduction peak with potential -0.68 V, while Mo(py)₃Cl₃ shows reversible one-electron reduction⁴ at potential, -1.45 V. Thus substitution by TPP causes a marked decrease in potential at which the reduction occurs. This is an expected trend in view of stronger π -acceptor character of TPP.

The compound, Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ was subjected to various reactions and the Mo complexes obtained therefrom is described in Experimental. The reactions of acetone and acetonitrile are those of donor solvents substituting one TPP as

Both the reactions are quantitative and the preferential substitution of TPP indicates inertness of Mo-N (py) over Mo-P (TPP) bond. The ir spectrum of the acetone-adduct gives the characteristic C=O band at 1715 cm⁻¹ while ¹H nmr spectrum gives proton resonance at δ 2.0 (CH₃) and 7.7 (ArH) with peak intensity ratio of 1 : 3.3. The acetonitrile adduct is confirmed by the ir spectrum with characteristic $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ band at 2100 cm⁻¹.

Nitrosylation of Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ gives Mo(py)(NO)(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ with characteristic ν_{NO} band at 1770 cm⁻¹. The reaction stoichiometry is as

The NOCl was analyzed by absorbing in aqueous bicarbonate followed by determination of NO₂⁻ with Ce^{IV} and Cl⁻ as AgCl. The nitrosylation process can be explained by the scheme proposed by Rakshit *et al.*⁶, in which NO disproportionates to NO⁺ and NO⁻; the latter replaces

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd.	Mo% : Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$
Mo(py)(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl ₃	11.2 (11.7)	3.92	5.5 ^a 6.7 ^b 9.5 ^c
Mo(py)(CH ₃ COCH ₃)(PPh ₃)Cl ₃	15.9 (16.0)	3.31	8.2 ^a
Mo(py)(CH ₃ CN)(PPh ₃)Cl ₃	16.3 (16.4)	3.30	8.0 ^a
Mo(py)(NO)(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	12.3 (12.0)	3.65	8.1 ^a
Mo ₂ (PPh ₃) ₃ Cl ₄	17.3 (17.1)	0.99	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, P and Cl analyses. **In :
^aDMSO, ^bacetone, ^cacetonitrile.

Cl⁻ from the coordination zone while the former gives NOCl.

Hydrogen at elevated temperature causes reduction of Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ with partial decomposition of TPP. Product analysis corresponds to the equation,

The benzene vapor (PhH) produced was scrubbed through methanol and estimated spectrophotometrically⁷ at 256 nm by comparing with a standard benzene in the same solvent. PH₃ was absorbed/oxidized in H₂O₂-H₂SO₄ scrubber and the resulting PO₄³⁻ was determined alkalimetrically as ammonium phosphomolybdate, while the sublimate Py.HCl was analyzed for N and Cl. The product, Mo₂(PPh₃)₃Cl₄ is completely insoluble and has low magnetic moment, suggesting metal-metal interaction. The proposed dimeric formula is a tentative one and higher degree polymerization can not be ruled out.

Experimental

The starting material, (NH₄)₂[Mo(H₂O)Cl₅] was prepared by the method described earlier⁸. Hydrogen and nitric oxide were prepared in the laboratory, purified and dried.

Conductance was measured on a Philips P9030 RCI bridge. Electronic diffuse reflectance spectrum (film) was recorded on a Cary 17/D spectrophotometer with magnesium carbonate as reference, UV-VIS solution spectrum on a Varian-Techtron spectrophotometer, ir spectrum on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectrum on a Hitachi R600 instrument. CV was measured on a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system. A three-electrode measurement was carried out with a Beckman 39273 platinum inlay electrode in conjunction with Pt-wire auxiliary electrode, a saturated calomel electrode with tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) as supporting electrolyte. Magnetic measurement was made with a Gouy balance at room temperature.

For analysis, compounds were decomposed by digestion with H₂SO₄ and H₂O₂ (30%). Phosphorus was determined alkalimetrically as ammonium phosphomolybdate⁵. After decomposition of the compounds with H₂SO₄, molybdenum was determined by reduction to Mo^{III} using Jone's reductor followed by titrimetry. For analysis of chlorine, the compounds were decomposed by fusion with Na₂CO₃-Na₂O₂ mixture and from the aqueous extract Cl was estimated gravimetrically as AgCl⁵. C, H and N were determined by microanalysis.

Preparations : The primary starting material for all

the subsequent preparations was Mo(py)₃Cl₃. It was prepared² by refluxing (NH₄)₂[Mo(H₂O)Cl₅] with 1 : 1 pyridine-ethanol mixture for 2 h. Yellow crystals that separated on cooling, was washed successively with water and ethanol and dried under vacuum.

Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ : A mixture of Mo(py)₃Cl₃ (50 mg) and TPP (100 mg) (~ 1 : 3.5 mole) was gradually heated to 70° in dry CO₂ atmosphere. The melt was then cooled and excess TPP was removed by washing with benzene. The product, on drying under vacuum, yielded a brown powder (30 mg) which was freely soluble in DMSO, acetone and acetonitrile but sparingly in methanol and benzene.

Mo(py)(CH₃COCH₃)(PPh₃)Cl : Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ (50 mg) was refluxed with acetone (10 ml) for 4 h on a water-bath. A brown solution was formed leaving behind a trace of solid. The solution, after filtration, was evaporated under vacuum to give a sticky mass which on repeated washing with benzene yielded a brown powder (35 mg), soluble both in acetone and DMSO.

Mo(py)(CH₃CN)(PPh₃)Cl₃ : It was obtained in a manner similar to propanone complex starting from Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ (40 mg) and acetonitrile (10 ml). The brown solid product (35 mg) was soluble in CH₃CN and DMSO.

Mo(py)(NO)(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ : Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ (50 mg) was heated at 85 ± 5° in a stream of pure and dry nitric oxide gas for 2 h. The exit gas was passed through a AgNO₃ (in decimolar HNO₃) scrubber to trap gaseous chloride, if any. To avoid NO₂ formation, an inert CO₂ atmosphere was maintained before and after the reaction. The green product (50 mg) was soluble in acetone, CH₃CN and DMSO.

Mo₂(PPh₃)₃Cl₄ : Mo(py)(PPh₃)₂Cl₃ (40 mg) was heated in a stream of pure dry H₂ gas for 2 h at 120 ± 5°. The product gases were analyzed as described earlier. After cooling, the residual product was washed with benzene and dried to yield the compound (37 mg) insoluble in common organic solvents.

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